

UNPACKING PARENTAL DECISION-MAKING: ATTITUDES, NORMS, AND SUPPORT SHAPING POLIO IMMUNISATION BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract

Purpose: The objective of the study is to explore the antecedents of parental intention behaviour on polio immunisation. Vaccine literacy is used as a moderator in this study. *Design/Methodology/ Approach:* For this purpose, the method of convenience sampling was used; the data were obtained from 200 individuals living mainly in the Hazara division of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Khawa, Pakistan. SPSS has been used for data analysis. *Findings:* The finding reveals that parental intention behaviour is significantly and positively affected by attitude and thus significantly impacts vaccine uptake. *Originality:* Vaccine literacy moderate's relationship between subjective norms & intention behaviour, government support & intention behaviour. Government support also positively influences the intention behaviour. *Implications:* The evidence from the current research study provides important and useful implications for hospitals and public health departments, healthcare professionals, policymakers, and the government, along with recommendations for future research.

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan is among the limited nations that still experience polio, even with massive measures being put to prevent the expand of the disease and make the world polio-free. Since 2000, Supplementary Immunisation Activities (SIAs) have also been held on an annual basis, since there was an outbreak of 119 cases of polio, reduced to 32 cases by 2007. Nonetheless, the spread persists, and it is hoped that all children below five years of age will receive several doses of Oral Polio Vaccine (OPV) in the high-endemic countries (Ahsan et al., 2021). Polio is avoidable, and the International Polio Eradication Program (GPEI), which began in 1988, has eliminated 99 cases of polio worldwide. Nevertheless, 1% of the world's poliomyelitis infections occur in Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Nigeria. The GPEI aims to eradicate it in 2023, with the vision of eradication, integration, and certification (Alonge, 2020). The polio eradication efforts in Pakistan have been slowed down, especially by COVID-19, caregiver burnout, and low vaccine coverage. New strategies will be required to counter such problems. Social norms, the role of vaccinators, and media campaigns are important influencing factors on attitudes toward vaccination. Individual health beliefs, peer pressure, and healthcare providers are also vital to influencing the decision to vaccinate (French et al., 2020). People are reluctant to be vaccinated despite the effectiveness of immunisation, particularly in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. The causes of this hesitancy include misinformation, absence of safety information, risk perception, and distrust of science. These are psychological and social considerations that affect the attitude of parents and their choices in vaccination. The issue of distrust that leads to conspiracy theories concerning medical knowledge can be resolved by introducing public health reforms aimed at creating trust and stimulating the process of vaccination (SADIA & ARFAN LATIF, 2025). The presented research is based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), and it will consider the role of parental knowledge, attitudes, and trust in health care professionals on vaccination intention, as well as the importance of trust in overcoming vaccine hesitancy (Khayyam et al., 2022).

Only three countries, such as Pakistan, are still endemic with Polio, and the country has made efforts to reduce the transmission of Polio without success. Supplementary Immunisation Activities (SIAs) initiated in 2000 through door-to-door delivery of Oral Polio Vaccine (OPV) decreased cases to 32 by 2007 from 119 cases. It has, however, slightly increased cases after 2008, and in 2011, Pakistan had the highest number of poliomyelitis infections, and this incites some concern in regard to the role played by this country as the last host of the virus. This scenario was a great challenge to the Global Polio Eradication Initiative (Ahsan et al., 2021). Some past studies, such as the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), have studied parental intentions on vaccination, taking into account such factors as social campaigns, peer influence, and personal values. Nevertheless, the influence of parental behaviour, vaccine literacy, and government support will be studied in this research, and the quantitative method will be used to investigate the impact of parental hesitancy on the results of vaccinations (Khayyam et al., 2022).

This study investigates the behavioural determinants of parental decision-making regarding polio immunisation. Specifically, it explores whether parental attitudes significantly influence their intention to vaccinate their children and examines the extent to which subjective norms shape these intentions. The research further evaluates the role of government support in motivating parental participation in polio immunisation campaigns and assesses how parental intention translates into actual immunisation behaviour. Additionally, the moderating effect of vaccine literacy is analysed to determine whether it strengthens or weakens the relationship between parental attitudes, subjective norms, government support, and their intention to immunise. By integrating these factors, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the psychosocial and contextual drivers that influence polio immunisation uptake.

As discussed above, many factors help to shape the intention and behaviour of parents toward immunisation. Here, we are discussing only the polio vaccine because Pakistan is still among the three countries in the world that are still fighting to

interrupt the transmission of the polio virus. The variables we are using here haven't been used before, especially regarding the polio vaccine, and the majority research work done was qualitative in nature. In this, we will try to figure out the relationship of parental attitude and behaviour with respect to subjective norms and government support, with the moderating effect of vaccine literacy. The Immunization Intentions and behavior is Measured on the basis of theory of planned behavior (TPB) and a quantitative questionnaire, were used to predict parents' intentions for under 5 years of age vaccination against polio mellitus virus.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Vaccination is the best prevention of infectious diseases, regardless of rumours spread and conspiracy theories. Research conducted at Imperial College London pointed out that vaccine resistance slowed down COVID-19 therapies. The cognitive, emotional, societal, and political factors impact decisions on individual vaccination, which requires interventions supported by theories. The study conducted by Abd Rahman et al. (2024) explains that the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) plays a significant role in explaining the behaviour in vaccination, and the intention is provoked by the attitude, subjective norms, and perceived control. Twum et al. (2021) suggest that the use of TPB has been demonstrated in different health settings, such as immunisation. The Increasing Vaccination Model developed by WHO considers the factors that affect vaccine adoption. Despite the broad usage of TPB, it has some limitations, including failure to consider the effects of emotions on behaviour. Hagger et al. (2020) by study uses TPB to study the problem of COVID-19 vaccination in South Asian populations in terms of cognitive, emotional, and relational perspectives.

H1: The perceived intention positively and significantly affects the behaviour.

The rate of immunisation between regions is different and depends on personal beliefs and values, and the availability of vaccines. Lack of vaccines has been the result of vaccine hesitancy, especially in populations of distrust or lack of knowledge, which causes outbreaks and low coverage. According to the

Dyda et al. (2020) Vaccine Confidence Project and Welcome Global Monitor, individuals are highly influenced by attitudes and beliefs, which influence the uptake of vaccines and are influenced by societal, emotional, and cognitive factors. The Social Contagion Theory, that perceptions about vaccinations are transmitted within the social group, and community involvement is highly important to achieve acceptance (Konstantinou et al., 2021). There is a correlation of socioeconomic factors with increased vaccine acceptance, which include education and income. Similarly, in the study by Fridman et al. (2021), Vaccine behaviour is also dependent on political ideology (particularly in the U.S.), where liberals and conservatives have varying amounts of scepticism. Low education and misinformation diminish vaccine acceptance in low-income countries. Such strategies as community engagement and transparency can boost uptake (Shakeel et al., 2022). The resistance of parents, which is predetermined by prejudice and views of health bodies, is a serious inconvenience (SteelFisher et al., 2022). The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) has been proven to be useful in explaining the behaviours related to vaccination (Ahsan et al., 2021). The causes of vaccine hesitancy in Nigeria include cultural, political, and economic aspects (Galadima et al., 2021).

H2: The attitude has a positive as well as significant influence on intention behaviour.

Misinformation, personal beliefs, and community issues affect the vaccination coverage; positively rated social norms and community attitudes favour increased vaccine acceptance (Konstantinou et al., 2021). The demographic variables, such as education and income, also influence the behaviour of vaccination, and the higher the education, the higher the acceptance of vaccines. The resistance to vaccines is a matter of political ideology, especially in some groups (Fridman et al., 2021). Poor information and the availability of unreliable information are Factors that led to vaccine hesitancy in low-income countries. Open communication, community participation, health professional recommendations, and improved vaccine coverage are essential to work on (Shakeel et al., 2022). Polio is a major issue in Pakistan, and in some places, such as Khyber

Pakhtunkhwa, lack of security, misinformation, and culture have reduced the use of vaccines. Peshawar study revealed that religious beliefs, migration, and not being educated are the reasons, and some specific intervention is required (Shafique et al., 2021).

H3: Subjective norm significantly and positively affects the intention to behave.

As a densely populated, poorly developed country in South Asia, Pakistan has serious problems in polio eradication, where 15 per cent of the population is below five, and the rate of childhood mortality is high. According to the study by Rahim et al. (2022), some 60% of children are vulnerable to vaccine-preventable diseases. Religions, false information, and conspiracy theories play a role in vaccine denial, especially in the northern parts, where security and militancy a barriers to vaccination. Started in 1994 under the support of the government of Pakistan, the WHO, UNICEF, among others, the Global Polio Eradication Initiative (GPEI) has suffered a setback because of political instability and terrorism. As per the study by Burkholder et al. (2023), the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 interfered with polio campaigns, making them more vulnerable to vaccine-preventable diseases. Vaccine acceptance and coverage can be improved by door-to-door campaigns and community involvement, as well as positive social norms (SteelFisher et al., 2022).

H4: Government support positively and significantly affects the intention behaviour.

The present study focuses on the issue of vaccine hesitancy in Saudi Arabia and how health literacy and awareness can help raise the vaccination rates. Myhre et al. (2020) observe how Parental education about the advantages and risks of vaccines and their safety increases confidence and self-efficacy to make decisions. The issue of side effects is a significant source of reluctance, and 21.93% of the participants say that they are not sure, and 49.45% are planning to get the COVID-19 vaccine (Sadiqa, 2023). In a survey on 447 Italian parents, it was established that trust in healthcare systems has a significant impact on the intention to vaccinate (Caso et al., 2022). Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) implies that cognitive and behavioural determinants can be applied in decisions regarding vaccines (Caso et al.,

2022). Indeed, there is evidence that trust and recommendations by community members boost the level of vaccination in China (Wang et al., 2022). Facebook, in particular, social media, is central to vaccine acceptance (Limaye et al., 2021). Vaccine acceptance increased due to awareness activities in Ghana (Addy et al., 2024), which suggests the importance of efficient communication strategies.

In this study, the authors have shown that vaccine literacy is one of the major factors that lead to overcoming vaccine hesitancy, and so, in Saudi Arabia, as well. Health literacy leads to vaccine literacy, which is the need to educate people on the advantages, risks, and procedures of vaccines (Kanan et al., 2024). It focuses on positive communication and community involvement to increase vaccine willingness. The COVID-19 pandemic only indicated the significance of vaccine literacy in overcoming hesitancy based on socioeconomic conditions, religious views, and fake news (Shakeel et al., 2022). Research demonstrates that positive attitudes toward vaccination among social groups make them accept the vaccines more (Paul et al., 2021). According to the European Health Literacy Survey (Michel & Goldberg, 2021), education, health literacy, and improved health outcomes are also interconnected, and vaccination education should be promoted in healthcare practices. The improvement of the communication of healthcare providers is an essential element of developing trust and raising the level of coverage.

H5: vaccine literacy moderates attitude & intention behaviour.

H6: vaccine literacy moderates subjective norms & intention behaviour.

H7: vaccine literacy moderates government support & intention behaviour.

As it is mentioned earlier that this research study is about revealing the antecedents of parental behaviour on polio immunisation using parental attitude, subjective norms, and government support as independent variables, whereas intention behaviour is used as dependent behaviour with the moderating role of vaccine literacy. In light of above mentioned literature, the suggested research model is demonstrated as below:

Figure 1. Suggested Research Model: Revealing the antecedents of parental behaviour on polio immunisation with the moderating role of vaccine literacy

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research looks at the relationship between parents’ intention and the intentions antecedent, and the immunisation of children as a result of this antecedent, on the immunisation of children and the theory of planned behaviour. Similarly, Dyda et al. (2020) study identifies the concentration on parental attitudes, subjective norms, intention behaviour, government support, and the mediating factor of vaccine literacy. According to previous studies by Dyda et al. (2020), a quantitative study is the most appropriate to investigate the connections between these variables. Behavioural intentions are shaped by attitude, which is determined by beliefs (Yuniarwati et al., 2022). Decisions are made under social pressure, due to subjective norms (Ahsan et al., 2021). Legal enforcement, penalties, and education of the population on vaccines can boost the uptake of immunisation. Health literacy encompasses disease prevention, health education, and immunisation as its components, vaccine literacy (Okan et al., 2023). The intended behaviour is the

behaviour that responds to the external stimuli and internal situations that affect the choice of vaccination. The respondents are voluntary participants in Hazara, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, where data has been collected through the use of an online questionnaire. To get valid and rational responses, participants were told the ethical standards, privacy, and confidentiality. After the questionnaire finalisation for the survey purpose, responses were collected, so that participants of the study were reached out to. The step of collecting the data from the respondents stretched over a period of 6 weeks, starting from May 1st, 2023, to June 16th, 2023. Research respondents were given ample amount of time in order to complete and submit their answers, which ultimately led to the acquisition of a dataset that served to be more consistent and reliable.

3.1 Population and Sampling

The population of this study consists of individuals having a child under 5 years of age who reside in Hazara, KPK, Pakistan, since it is intended to investigate aspects that influence polio immunisation during childhood. The study is based on

convenience sampling due to time limitations. The data will be collected from the parents of children under 5 years of age, the rationale for which is that data collection from this population was easy and convenient. 200 participants were requested to fill out the questionnaire. A suitable number of questionnaires were distributed with the help of an online link to around 220 individuals living in Hazara, KPK, based on a convenience sampling technique, out of which 201 people completed and submitted them, yielding a response rate of 91.2%.

3.2 Scales and Measures

The survey questionnaire was further subdivided into seven questions: demographics, subjective norms, vaccination attitude, parental vaccination intention, vaccination behaviour, vaccine literacy, and government support. Evaluation was carried out on all items, with alterations of wordings to fit the context.

- **Intention Behaviour:** Evaluated using hierarchical regression and structural equation modelling based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour. Attitude, subjective norms, and intention affect behaviour, with perceived behavioural control moderating the mediation (Yarmohammadi et al., 2023).
- **Vaccine Literacy (VL):** Assessed through a self-reported questionnaire adapted from the Ishikawa test for chronic non-communicable diseases, validated for content and construct.
- **Government Support:** Utilised the COVID-SCORE survey instrument with satisfactory validity, adapted to measure public perceptions of government responses (Lazarus et al., 2020).

- **Attitude and Subjective Norms:** Adapted a scale with four items each for attitude and subjective norms (Abd Rahman et al., 2024).

3.3 Data Analysis Procedure

The primary component of this study is data analysis. Using the right data collection and analysis methodologies, researchers can draw a firm conclusion regarding their study project. The next step after data has been gathered for a research project is the analysis of the data. To do this, a variety of techniques are employed. The knowledge obtained from the study participants is first processed and organised into the desired order. It is crucial to complete this step to prepare the data collected for further investigation. For the goal of conducting data analysis, numerous software programs are being used. In this study, SPSS is used for data analysis. Data analysis can be divided into several steps.

3. FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Table 1 reports valid answers of 200 respondents, the mean value is between 4 to 5.5, and the standard deviation of 1.4-1.7. The data is generally distributed, with a small degree of skewness of a few variables (Cain et al., 2017; Jammalamadaka et al., 2021). The Pearson correlation test was used to determine the strength, direction, as well as magnitude of the relationships between variables (Berman, 2016). Findings indicate a high level of correlation whereby the Subjective Norms (SN) are closely correlated with Attitude (ATT) ($r = 0.716$), Vaccine Confidence Index (VCI) ($r = 0.710$), among others. Intentional Behaviour (IB) and Vaccine Literacy had the lowest correlation ($r = 0.149$).

Table 1. Descriptive and Correlation

	Mean	SD	SN	VCI	ATT	GV	VB	VL
SN	5.0367	1.68972	1	.710**	.716**	.626**	.567**	.217**
VC	5.4067	1.60963	.710**	1	.758**	.702**	.607**	.186**
I								
AT	5.1362	1.53759	.716**	.758**	1	.668**	.714**	.222**
T								
GV	4.9272	1.53244	.626**	.702**	.668**	1	.568**	.145*
IB	5.0538	1.65013	.567**	.607**	.714**	.568**	1	.149*
VL	4.4577	1.38375	.217**	.186**	.222**	.145*	.149*	1

4.1 Regression Analysis

The results of the fitness of the model using ANOVA have also been presented by the researcher in Table 2. For this purpose, the researcher has applied the F-test of significance. This test can ascertain that the regression model used in a study is a good fit in comparison to the impact of the model in the absence of the predictors (Kissell & Poserina, 2017). The F-calculated value and significance level results show that the impact of GV, SN, ATT, and VCI on IB is a good fit, as the F-value test is significant.

Table 2. ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	300.617	4	75.154	54.773	.000 ^b
Residual	267.559	195	1.372		
Total	568.176	199			

4.1.1 Direct Effects

This study tested seven hypotheses, with four showing direct effects. The first hypothesis, proposing a positive effect of the Vaccine Confidence Index (VCI) on Intentional Behaviour (IB), was insignificant ($\beta = 0.082, p = 0.1$). The second hypothesis, stating Attitude (ATT) positively influences IB, was supported ($\beta = 0.589, p = 0.1$). The third hypothesis, regarding Subjective Norms (SN), was rejected ($p = 0.513$). The fourth hypothesis, linking Government Support (GV) to IB, was accepted ($\beta = 0.136, p = 0.092$), indicating a 13.6% increase in IB.

Table 3. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.635	.318		1.993	.048
	SN	.051	.079	.050	.655	.513
	VCI	.082	.090	.078	.908	.365
	ATT	.589	.092	.536	6.402	.000
	GV	.136	.081	.124	1.693	.092

a. Dependent Variable: VB

4.1.2 Moderation Analysis

The research explored the Vaccine Literacy (VL) as an intermediate between the Attitude (ATT), Government Support (GV), Subjective Norms (SN), and Intentional Behaviour (IB). Stepwise regression analysis (hierarchical regression) revealed that ATT and GV had a significant effect on Vaccine Behaviour (VB), whereby they explained 72.6% of variability, as shown in Table 4. The inclusion of moderation variables boosted R-squared to 0.992, which is an improvement in the explanatory power of the model (Richardson et al., 2015).

Table 4. Hierarchical Regression

Independent variables	M1(β)	M2 (β)
ATT	.622**	.589***
GV	.161**	.427***
SN	.072	.002
R ²	.726	
Moderator		
VLXATT		-.111***
VLXGV		-.087***

VLXSN	.194***
R ²	.992
ΔR ²	.266

4. DISCUSSION

The following chapter 4 offers the specific analysis of the study, which examines the antecedents of the parental intention behaviour in terms of polio immunisation. The research has been moderated with vaccine literacy and convenience sampling to gather the data of 200 people in Hazara, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. To address the moderating effect of vaccine literacy on attitude, subjective norms, governmental support, and immunisation intention behaviour, the stepwise regression analysis was used to identify the moderation (Richardson et al., 2015).

The Pearson correlation analysis is described in Table 3 with significant positive relationships among variables (Berman, 2016). ATT (r=0.758, p<0.01) and GV (r=0.702), VB (r=0.607), and VL (r=0.186) have the strongest correlation with VCI. ATT has a significant correlation with GV (r=0.668), VB (r=0.714), and VL (r=0.222). There is also a significant positive correlation between GV and VB (r=0.568). But, the effect of VCI on VB, as indicated in Table 5, is positive (=0.082), but not significant (p > 0.1). Such findings are contrary to the past research by (Ahsan et al., 2021; Caso et al., 2022; Hagger et al., 2020), who endorse the Theory of Planned Behaviour.

ATT and VB are significantly and positively associated, and it is evident from the results in Table 5, which also shows that the hypothesis was accepted as the β value of 0.589 exists between ATT and VB, and the p-value is below 0.1, so it can be said that ATT has a 58.9% effect on VB for a one-unit increase. This finding is consistent with the results of a previous studies done by (Ahsan et al., 2021; SteelFisher et al., 2022), psychosocial factors can also play an important role in shaping up of attitude regarding immunization in children so because of that Theory of Planned Behavior is used in current study including both proximal and distal factors that can build up the intention. Human Attitude results in Human intention that can either be in favour or

against to so Attitude can be regarded as the extent to which a person agrees or disagrees.

The results show that this hypothesis was also rejected as the p-value was 0.513, which is above 0.1. So the relationship between these two is insignificant and negative. The finding is found to be non-analogous to a study conducted by (Ahsan et al., 2021; Fridman et al., 2021). With regards to previous studies, it is emphasised that societal influence affects the intention to vaccinate, and society is more at risk of developing diseases when faced with vaccine hesitancy. Positive subjective norms positively correlated with stronger intention to vaccination, whereas negative attitudes led to conspiracy beliefs.

The findings of the current study support this hypothesis. The p-value of the relation between government support and intention behaviour was 0.092, and the β value of 0.136 exists between GV and VB, showing that if one unit is observed in GV, it leads to an increase of 13.6% in VB. The finding is found to be analogous to a study conducted by (Butt et al., 2020; Chauhan et al., 2023). The Polio development in Pakistan evidences how the government assistance influences behaviour. Socioeconomic, political, and geopolitical factors cause vaccine hesitancy; however, active government intervention and cooperation in the case of international relations can resolve this issue.

The moderating impact of Vaccine Literacy in the model was investigated. The VL moderation was investigated among Attitude and intention behaviour, Subjective Norm and intention behaviour, and Government support and intention behaviour. The researcher used a stepwise regression analysis to analyse VL's moderation effects, also known as hierarchical regression (Richardson et al., 2015). The stepwise regression in Table 6 depicted that independent variables (ATT, GV) had a significant influence on the intention behaviour (72.6% variance), and the moderation variables increased R-squared to 99.2%. The relationship was moderated by vaccine literacy and hurt ATT/GV and a negative impact on SN.

The study has essential practical implications not only to healthcare institutions but also to the government authorities, other public health professionals, and policymakers. The results underscore the fact that the awareness among individuals related to the health benefits of immunisation is a key factor in influencing the positive attitudes towards polio vaccination. Ittefaq et al. (2024) observation suggests that medical workers, social leaders, and social influencers must teach the population about the safety of vaccines, eliminate conspiracies, and emphasise the harmfulness of polio. Cherian and Mantel (2020) observe that Government support is essential in improving the use of vaccines and promoting the immunisation policies. There should be a liaison between the national and international agencies, such as the WHO. The article emphasises the importance of attitude and community engagement in achieving favourable intentions for vaccination. It is necessary to provide effective guidance and educational material on immunisation to make informed decisions. The community level of knowledge dissemination is associated with a positive impact on parental behaviour and increasing the awareness of the health benefits of polio vaccination. The government should control the policy of immunisation in various provinces so that the majority of children can be vaccinated. There is a need to improve vaccine literacy through public health campaigns and integrated communication strategies because it greatly affects the uptake of vaccines. The government's collaboration with NGOs to improve vaccine literacy to advance further to break polio transmission should be more emphasised by policymakers (Lohiniva et al., 2022). The study also emphasises the importance of government intervention to fight fake news and guarantee the presence of vaccination. Introducing a law that would make vaccination a compulsory procedure and penalising the non-vaccination population would also serve the population health objectives. Moreover, investigating new routes of vaccination, including the intramuscular inoculation with the polio vaccine, would also enhance the immunisation efforts.

5.1 Limitations and Directions for Future Research

This research has few limitations in several ways that the researcher will consider in the future. The sample is Hazara, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, which cannot be generalised, and future research needs to be diversified to other provinces and developing nations. It would also be worth investigating urban and rural settings. Because polio has been almost eliminated all over the world, research on its elimination, especially in Pakistan, should be provided. The non-probability sampling method might not give the complete picture of the population, and therefore, stratified sampling is advisable. The time constraints have restricted the sample size, which limits the generalizability, and thus the future research ought to be conducted with the aim of increasing the size of the sample. The originality of the research is that the authors examine the behaviour of parents, attitudes, vaccine literacy, and government support in relation to polio vaccination based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour.

5. Conclusion

Misconceptions, conspiracy theories, and geopolitical issues, such as terrorism in Pakistan, especially in Balochistan and KPK, and socioeconomic issues, have been influential in the eradication of polio in the country. Vaccine literacy and governmental support can be critical in dealing with these problems. Attitudes and behavioural intentions towards polio vaccination can be positively changed by means of the enhancement of health and vaccine literacy in society. Community leaders can be engaged in countries such as Pakistan, where there is a strong societal influence, and this will ensure that change is brought. Moreover, anti-vaccination and misinformation policies can also be used to help eradicate them. On the basis of 200 respondents, this work established that vaccine literacy has a positive influence on attitudes, intentions, and subjective norms in addition to government support. The study brings out that parental care about their health has a direct impact on the intentions to vaccinate the child, which can be boosted by an improved level of vaccine literacy to considerable levels. These results are valuable to enhance positive

practices in relation to vaccination in the community.

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